

Cortical structure in provisional and chronic tic disorders

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Abstract

Background: Structural MRI studies have found thinning of various cerebral cortical regions in people with Tourette syndrome (TS) compared to tic-free controls (TFC).

Whether this thinning precedes or follows the first tic is unknown; cortical structure has not been studied in the first year after tic onset (Provisional Tic Disorder, PTD).

Objectives: Compare regional cortical thickness and surface area in PTD, TS and TFC.

Methods: T1-weighted brain MRI was acquired in 391 children 5-10 years old: 83 with PTD, 103 with TS or chronic motor tic disorder, and 205 TFC. Over half of scans used prospective motion correction to minimize error due to head movement. FreeSurfer measured regional cortical thickness and surface area. ANCOVA models compared these measurements by group, controlling for age, sex, handedness, scanner and brain volume. Significance was corrected for multiple comparisons.

Results: Brain volume and mean cortical thickness were lower in TS than TFC, with PTD intermediate (TS<PTD<TFC), as were most cortical regions. The typical developmental cortical thinning over this age range occurred twice as fast in children with tics. By contrast, bilateral insula surface area followed the pattern PTD<TS<TFC. Insula appears to be smaller at tic onset.

Conclusion: These data suggest that the thinner cortex in TS develops after tics begin, and thus may represent a consequence than a cause of tics. It may reflect earlier

maturation of inhibitory circuits developed with extended experience suppressing tics. By contrast, the smaller insula may contribute to causing tics, perhaps via its role in the action-mode network.

Introduction

Chronic tic disorders including Tourette syndrome (hereinafter, TS) are defined by unwanted, repeated movements and vocalizations (tics) that collectively occur over a period of one year or more.¹ Tics differ from other movement disorders in that they are relatively stereotyped but nonrhythmic, can be suppressed with effort for a period of time, and are often preceded by focal or generalized sensory phenomena or an urge to tic.²

In vivo structural MRI studies have found thinner precentral and/or postcentral gyrus in TS compared to tic-free controls (TFC).³⁻⁸ These gyri contain primary motor cortex (M₁) and primary somatosensory cortex (S₁). This finding has been taken as supporting a model of tic disorders as characterized by hyperarousal, deficits in sensorimotor gating, and impaired cortical inhibition.⁹ Structural MRI studies of TS have also shown thinning in other cortical regions including insula and orbital cortex.^{4-6, 10, 11} These regions belong to the brain's social decision-making network, dysfunction in which is hypothesized to explain important features of TS.¹²⁻¹⁴ However, not all studies found precentral gyrus thinning,^{8, 10} and other regions were very inconsistently identified, leaving uncertainty about which cortical areas are truly thinner in tic patients. Some of these studies examined children and adults, and most included relatively small samples. Only one study reported on the surface area of cortical regions in TS, and it identified no significant differences from children without tics.⁸

Crucially, whether cortical thinning represents a cause or an effect of ticcing is unknown.

Chronic ticcing or adaptation to chronic ticcing could result in structural changes to cortical regions.¹⁵ By contrast, cortical thinning present when tics begin, or immediately after, would support the interpretation that the pathophysiology underlying thinner cortex may cause tics. Unfortunately, previous studies focused on chronic tic disorders; none measured cortical thickness during the first year after tic onset (*i.e.*, Provisional Tic Disorder, PTD).

We therefore examined structural MRI data from children ages 5-10 years with PTD, TS, or no tics. Our only *a priori* hypothesis was that both TS and PTD would show thinner somatomotor cortex than tic-free controls (TFC) at the same age, but we also examined regions throughout the cortex for differences in thickness or surface area.

Methods

MR images from a total of 391 children ages 5-10 were analyzed for this study: 83 with PTD, 103 with TS and 205 TFC. This study was approved by the Washington University Human Research Protection Office (IRB), approvals 201109157 and 201707059. A parent or guardian gave informed consent to each child's participation in research. All children with PTD, along with 44 with TS and 26 TFC, were enrolled in the New Tics study.¹⁶ The remaining children's parents/guardians had previously given informed consent to share data from their participation in research with future research studies. Diagnosis for all patients with tics followed DSM-5 criteria¹ and was confirmed by a physician experienced in TS and other tic disorders (authors KJB or BLS).

All participants had a T₁-weighted MRI of the brain (MP-RAGE sequence) with 0.5-1.0

mm³ voxels on either a Siemens Trio or Prisma scanner; 217 of the scans were performed with prospective motion correction (vNavs) to minimize partial volume effect from head motion during scan acquisition (see Supplemental Table 1).^{17, 18}

If a participant had more than one MP-RAGE image at a given age, the image with the highest *snr_total* value from MRIQC software was used in the analysis.¹⁹ FreeSurfer v. 7.3.2 with the Computational Anatomy Toolbox (CAT12) was used to measure thickness and surface area of 34 cortical regions in each hemisphere and to estimate brain volume (eTIV and total gray plus white matter volume, GM+WM).²⁰⁻²⁵ The cortical parcellation by FreeSurfer was visually reviewed for all participants (original N = 406), and 15 scans with incorrect identification of the cortical ribbon were excluded.

Clinical variables were compared using Fisher's exact test for categorical variables and unpaired t test or ANOVA for quantitative variables. Whole-brain effects of diagnosis were tested by a general linear model (GLM) controlling for age, sex and handedness. Dependent variables were brain volume (eTIV and GM+WM), total surface area, and weighted mean cortical thickness (regional mean thickness weighted by regional surface area).

We also examined cortical thickness and surface area in all 34 cortical regions in each hemisphere, with a GLM controlling for age, sex, handedness and scanner. Surface area was scaled by (GM+WM)^{2/3} to correct for areal differences attributable to differences in brain volume. The cortical thickness model omitted brain volume, as it was not significantly associated with thickness, conditional on other covariates. Multiple

comparisons correction for the 68 regions used Holm's method with a family-wise Type I error (FWE) rate of $\leq .05$ as the criterion for significance.²⁶ To minimize type II error, we also report regional significance using the less stringent false discovery rate (FDR) correction (Figure 1 and Supplemental Table 2). While all previous studies reported thickness, we also examined regional surface area because this measure has been important in similar analyses of other childhood-onset neuropsychiatric disorders.²⁷⁻²⁹

Exploratory analyses included the following. Cortical thickness or surface area in regions with a significant diagnosis-related group difference was tested for correlation with YGTSS total tic score (TTS) after accounting for age and sex. Next, after predicting regional thickness or area for each child based on the age and sex of the child using the TFC group data, the prediction error for children with tics (observed - predicted) was plotted against duration of illness (measured as days between tic onset and the scan), available for all PTD participants and 74 TS participants. The date of tic onset was estimated carefully in PTD as previously described in detail.^{30, 31} We also tested for correlations of regional thickness among cortical regions.

Results

Sample description

Table 1 summarizes the demographics of the sample by group, and the severity and duration of the tic disorder for the PTD and TS groups. The minimum duration of tics in the PTD group was 32 days (1 month) and the median was 128 days (4 months). The groups differed significantly by age and sex, so these variables were included in the

statistical models for cortical structure. Medication records were incomplete for the TS and TFC groups, but in the 83 children with PTD, only 16 were taking any medication affecting the brain.*

Global effects of age, sex, handedness and scanner

Older children have larger brains (GM+WM, $p < .001$), boys have larger brains than girls ($p < 10^{-16}$), and brain volume was smaller in scans from the Trio than in the prospective motion-corrected Prisma scans ($p < .001$). Results were similar when brain volume was measured as eTIV. As for weighted mean cortical thickness, older children have thinner cortex ($p < .001$) and boys have thinner cortex than girls ($p < .001$); handedness, scanner and brain volume were not significant. Total cortical surface area, corrected for brain volume, increased with age ($p < .001$) and was 3.5% greater in boys than in girls ($p < .001$) and 2.9% smaller measured on the Trio ($p < .001$). Handedness had no statistically significant effects on any of these measures, except that non-dextral children had 3% lower GM+WM volume ($p = .048$; $p = .094$ for eTIV).

Global effects of diagnosis

Controlling for age, sex, handedness and scanner, brain volume (GM+WM) differed by diagnosis (TS < PTD < TFC; 3.4% smaller in PTD, $p = .007$, and 4.8% smaller in TS, $p < .001$). The cerebral cortex was thinner in TS than in TFC, controlling for age, sex,

* 6 melatonin, 5 a stimulant, 2 diphenhydramine, and 1 each clonidine, atomoxetine, fluoxetine, benzodiazepine, and cyproheptadine. These numbers add to more than 16 because 2 of the children taking melatonin also took a stimulant or atomoxetine. Two additional children took an unspecified medication that might possibly be brain active: "pill for energy" and "over-the-counter antihistamine." No child with PTD was taking a dopamine antagonist.

handedness and scanner. On average, cortex was about 1.4% thinner in TS (least squares mean 2.87 mm, $p < .001$) than in TFC (2.91 mm), with PTD intermediate (2.89 mm, 0.7% thinner, $p = .078$). Results were similar if eTIV was excluded from the model. Adding an age \times diagnosis interaction term to the model did not substantially increase variance explained, but descriptively, children with tics experienced faster cortical thinning than those without tics (Supplemental Figure 2).

After correction for age, sex, handedness, scanner, and the expected effects of brain volume, total cortical surface area was significantly smaller in PTD, with TS intermediate (1.57% in PTD, $p = .014$, and 1.07% smaller in TS, $p = .060$).

Regional cortical thickness

Numerous cortical regions showed significant differences in thickness by diagnosis, correcting for age, sex, handedness, scanner and multiple comparisons (Table 2 and Figure 1, A–D). Almost all such regions showed the pattern TS < PTD < TFC, based on least squares means. Three contiguous medial occipital regions were reversed, TS > PTD > TFC, in both hemispheres. Note that for all significant cortical regions but one, TS differed most from TFC, with PTD intermediate. The lone exception was left rostral middle frontal gyrus (PTD < TS < TFC). Primary sensorimotor cortex was thinner in TS than in TFC, but the PTD-TFC difference was not significant (see Supplemental materials).

Regional cortical surface area

As for surface area, five regions differed significantly by group, two in the order TS < PTD

< TFC (right lateral and medial orbitofrontal cortex, OFC), and three in the order PTD < TS < TFC (left and right insula and left lateral OFC; Table 2 and Figure 1 E-H).

Effects of illness severity or duration

Mean TTS (tic severity) was 18% higher in TS than in PTD (Table 1). However, cortical thickness did not correlate significantly with YGTSS total tic score (TTS) across the entire set of tic groups. This finding held regardless of correction for age, sex and scanner.

As noted, cortical thickness in the PTD group was intermediate between the TFC and TS groups. We thus examined mean cortical thickness in the PTD group as a function of time since tic onset, corrected for age and sex. Descriptively, cortical thickness in the PTD group at tic onset was similar to that of the TFC group, but diminished over the first year to match the TS group at one year after tic onset (Figure 2A). However, the slope over the first year did not differ significantly from zero, so this description should be taken as suggestive rather than definite. Results were similar in the children examined with prospective motion correction.

Insula surface area showed a different pattern, being numerically lower in the PTD group than in the TS group. Mean left and right insula surface area, extrapolated to the time of tic onset, was already lower than in the TFC group (-127 mm^2), and stayed similarly low at one year (-139 mm^2 , Figure 2B). The slope over the first year did not differ significantly from zero. Results were similar in the children examined with prospective motion correction.

Discussion

As noted in the introduction, previous *in vivo* structural MRI studies raised important questions about brain structure in TS, including the location and timing of cortical thinning. Additionally, most prior reports assumed that cortical thinning reflected a process that caused tics, though cross-sectional association with diagnosis does not imply causality. The present study helps resolve these questions by virtue of a larger sample size than any previous study and, importantly, by including for the first time many children in the first year after tic onset.

Cortical thinning

First, our results confirm earlier findings and suggest that in fact numerous cortical regions are thinner in TS. Likely the variable regions identified by each study reflects in part Type II errors that this larger sample minimizes. Second, cortical thinning is greater in magnitude in chronic than in recent-onset tics, and this is not due to any age difference between groups. The results suggest that thinning may not be apparent at tic onset, but emerges over the first year to match that of TS participants at one year's duration (Fig. 3A). These results do not fit with a hypothesized lesion causing tics. They suggest instead that enhanced cortical thinning develops over time after tic onset. Since cortical thinning is a well-known normative developmental process during this age range,³²⁻³⁵ cortical thinning in TS may represent accelerated maturation.

This early cortical maturation may reflect experience inhibiting tics, as most children with tics suppress or attempt to suppress their ticcing in the presence of other people for

much of the day, every day. Structural correlates of ongoing inhibition would be expected to develop gradually over time after the onset of tics, and to develop to a greater extent than in children without tics, who do not experience the same nearly constant effort to control unwanted actions. The findings in the present study align well with this model or framework. Furthermore, this model may explain why in other studies thinning in various cortical regions has correlated with greater tic severity.^{4, 5, 10} Fahim et al showed that progressive cortical thinning continued in TS from ages 10 to 25 years, though in 3 of 4 regions, linear regression in each group suggested that the thinning in TS would slow over that age interval so as to match the thickness of the TFC group by age 20–30.⁴ Given that tics generally improve from approximately 10 to 25 years of age, these results would be interpreted as reflecting decreased need to suppress tics over that time interval, plus the gradual development in TFC of inhibitory control for non-tic behavior.

Medial occipital cortical regions were significantly thicker rather than thinner in the tic groups (PTD 1.5%, TS 0.9% above TFC; see Supplemental Figure 3). The excess cortical thickness in these regions did not correlate with tic severity (Supplemental Figure 4).

These regions are functionally associated with vision, which is clinically unaffected in tic disorders, and explaining this finding remains opaque. Future studies should follow up on this result.

Decreased regional surface area

Surface area of the right orbitofrontal cortex followed the same pattern as mean cortical thickness, TS < PTD < TFC, and may also represent changes caused by chronic ticcing.

However, left and right insula surface area instead followed the pattern PTD < TS < TFC, and insula surface area extrapolated back to tic onset was already lower than in controls (Fig. 3B). This temporal pattern—being present in the first year after tic onset and by best estimate present at tic onset—is what one would expect from a structural abnormality that may *cause* tics.

The insula figures prominently in models of the urge to tic.^{14, 36} These models are based on functional and structural neuroimaging studies of chronic tic disorders, whose results relate anterior insula to tics and to the urge to tic. Additional evidence comes from neuroimaging, EEG and lesion studies that implicate the insula and related brain regions in the urge to complete natural actions such as blinking or swallowing.³⁷⁻³⁹ The recently conceptualized Action-Mode Network (AMN), which prominently includes the anterior insula and anterior cingulate cortex, is proposed to be responsible for selecting and creating plans for physical actions.⁴⁰ The major output of the AMN is to the recently described Somato-Cognitive Action Network (SCAN),⁴¹ and signals propagate from the somatosensory and action plan creation portion of AMN to SCAN and the body representation areas of M₁.⁴² Recent work shows that focal lesions causing tics, and deep brain stimulation sites most linked to improvement in tic severity, are strongly functionally connected to the AMN and SCAN.⁴³ Moreover, fMRI studies show increased activation in the AMN during the time leading up to a tic.⁴⁴ Together, this circuitry suggests that a major cause of tics could be abnormal function of the AMN regions that develop, select or monitor action plans, or abnormal connectivity to the M₁ regions that implement them.

Limitations

The number of children with different tic disorder diagnoses were not balanced across scanners. However, this imbalance does not explain our key results. The children with PTD were more likely to be scanned on the Prisma, which was associated with thicker cortex, yet they had thinner cortex than did tic-free controls. Additionally, the GLM included a factor for scanner. Similarly, the sex ratio differed in the 3 groups, as expected, but the GLM accounted for sex. Importantly, since fewer than 1 in 5 of the PTD participants were taking any medication known to affect the brain, our results cannot be explained by medication effects.⁴⁵

Clinical tic severity over the week prior to the scan differed between the two tic groups (Table 1), though the groups do not differ to the degree considered clinically meaningful.⁴⁶ More importantly, the range of tic severity substantially overlaps in the two tic groups, and does not explain the group differences in cortical thickness or insula surface area (see Supplemental Figure 1).

Head movement during scan acquisition can lead to apparent artifactual thinning of the cortex.⁴⁷⁻⁵⁰ The finding that cortex was thinner if measured on the Trio without motion correction than on the Prisma with prospective motion correction is consistent with this known artifact. It is natural to wonder whether the presence during the scan of tics that moved the head created artifactual results. Again, however, this concern does not affect our key results. The Prisma vNav scans, which minimize movement-related effects on structural MRI,¹⁸ show the same differences by diagnostic group. We also used two

methods to discard scans with motion-related artifact. Additionally, tics are suppressible, and most of the children in these studies had practice holding still during MRI acquisition, including training in a mock scanner. Thus, tics on the day of the scan do not necessarily imply tics causing head movement during the scan acquisition.

Conclusion

The brain is slightly smaller and the cortex is thinner in children 5-10 years old who have TS than in tic-free controls, and less so in children the same age with tics for less than a year (TS < PTD < TFC). Numerous cortical regions contribute to this pattern. The thinner cortex in TS appears to begin at (not before) tic onset and progress gradually over the first nine years after tic onset. As such, cortical thinning is more likely to represent a consequence than a cause of tics. The data are consistent with the hypothesis that over time, chronic tic suppression affects brain structure in the same direction as does growth and maturation over this age range. These data also support the view that PTD represents not a different illness from TS but rather simply a way station in the progression of a chronic tic disorder.

By contrast, insula surface area is smaller in patients in the order PTD < TS < TFC, and the reduced insula surface area appears to have been present from the first tic. This temporal pattern is consistent with a region in which abnormal function could lead to tics. These results therefore add support for a causative role to previous functional and structural imaging studies that have associated the insula with the urge to move and with chronic tic disorders. We speculate that interventions early in the course of tic disorders

that target the insula, or brain networks that include the insula, may improve the clinical course.

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Tables

Table 1. Clinical characteristics

Counts or mean \pm S.D. are given.

Diagnosis	TFC	PTD	TS	<i>p</i>
N	205	83	103	—
Sex (F)	89	22	22	.0001
Handedness (nonR)	16	13	13	.11
Age (years)	8.95 \pm 1.42	7.71 \pm 1.69	9.16 \pm 1.49	< .0001
YGTSS TTS (0-50)	—	16.9 \pm 5.6	20.0 \pm 7.0 (N=95)	.0012
YGTSS impairment (0-50)	—	7.06 \pm 8.07	12.7 \pm 11.7 (N=92)	.0003
Duration of tic disorder (days)	—	151 \pm 86	1451 \pm 783 (N=74)	—

Table 2. Significant FWE-corrected p values for group differences

Corrected p_{FWE} values $<.05$ are shown. LHem = left hemisphere. RHem = right

hemisphere. The dagger † indicates a region whose least squares means were in the order

PTD < TS < TFC, and ‡ indicates TS > PTD > TFC. All others were TS < PTD < TFC. The

entry “.0000” means $<.00005$. * $p = .0501$.

Region	Cortical thickness		Surface area	
	p (LHem)	p (RHem)	p (LHem)	p (RHem)
banks of superior temporal sulcus	.0002	.0005		
caudal middle frontal	.0000	.0021		
cuneus	.0003 ‡	.0009 ‡		
fusiform	.0021	.0001		
inferior parietal	.0030			
inferior temporal	.0061			
lateral orbitofrontal	*		.0241 †	.0012
lingual	.0000 ‡	.0295 ‡		
medial orbitofrontal				.0002
middle temporal	.0005	.0259		
pars opercularis	.0002	.0129		
pars triangularis	.0171			
pericalcarine	.0000 ‡	.0000 ‡		
precentral	.0278			
rostral middle frontal	.0043 †			
superior frontal	.0013	.0075		
superior temporal	.0003	.0003		
insula	.0016		.0183 †	.0331 †

Figures

Figure 1. Group differences in cortical structure

All images show multiple-comparisons-corrected regional p values for group differences, with darker shades indicating lower p values. Shades of blue represent statistical significance after multiple comparisons correction. This map shows false discovery rate (FDR)-corrected p values (as $-\log_{10} p_{\text{FDR}}$). See Table 2 for the more stringent FWE-corrected p values. A–D, cortical thickness. E–H, surface area. A, C, E, G: left hemisphere. B, D, F, H: right hemisphere.

[figure on next page]

Figure 2. Key results by duration of tic disorder, corrected for age and sex

A: Mean cortical thickness for each participant, compared to the predicted value based on age and sex from the TFC group, plotted by days after tic onset. The TFC group is plotted in green circles at duration = 0. The PTD group is shown in blue triangles between 0 and 365 days, and the TS group is shown in burnt orange squares after 365 days.

B: Insula surface area (mean left and right hemisphere), with all other details as for A.

[figure on next page]

A

Supplemental materials

Primary sensorimotor cortex

Based on prior studies, we specified one *a priori* regional hypothesis; namely, that sensorimotor cortex would be thinner in children with tics. We tested this hypothesis by defining M₁S₁ in each participant as the average of bilateral mean precentral thickness (M₁) and bilateral mean postcentral thickness (S₁). An ANCOVA compared M₁S₁ between groups, controlling for age, sex, handedness, scanner (Trio or Prisma) and intracranial volume.

Testing this hypothesis showed that M₁S₁ cortical thickness was significantly smaller in TS than in TFC ($p = .006$), with least squares means TFC 2.499mm, PTD 2.494mm (-0.22%) and TS 2.464mm (-1.39%). The difference between PTD and TFC was not significant ($p = .7$). M₁S₁ also was smaller in boys than in girls ($p = .013$) and in those scanned on the Trio compared to the Prisma ($p = .025$). Thinning was significantly lower in TS vs. TFC in the motor cortex (M₁), but not in the postcentral gyrus (S₁).

In other words, the pattern of estimated mean sensorimotor cortex thickness was similar to that seen in the cerebral cortex taken as a whole, but here with the cortical thinning significant only in the chronic tic group. This was driven by thinning in motor cortex.

Supplemental Table 1. Acquisition details, by diagnostic group, for all MRI scans used in this analysis.

Scanner	Sequence	vNavs	Head Coil	TR (ms)	TE (ms)	TI (ms)	Voxel Size (mm)	TS	PTD	TFC
<i>Prisma, 166038</i>	tfl3d1_16ns\tfl_mgh_epinav_ABCD	YES	32-channel	2500	2.9	1070	1×1×1	18	0	0
<i>Prisma, 67064</i>	tfl3d1_16ns\tfl		64-channel	2400	2.22	1000	0.8×0.8×0.8	0	4	0
	tfl3d1_16ns\tfl_mgh_epinav_ABCD	YES	20-channel	2500	2.9	1070	1×1×1	0	0	54
	tfl3d1_16ns\tfl_mgh_epinav_ABCD	YES	64-channel	2500	2.9	1070	1×1×1	40	59	35
<i>Trio, 35177</i>	tfl3d1_16ns\tfl		12-channel	2200	2.34	1000	1×1×1	14	20	1
	tfl3d1_16ns\tfl		12-channel	2400	3.08– 3.17	1000	1×1×1	29	0	61
	tfl3d1_16ns\tfl_mgh_epinav_ABCD	YES	12-channel	2530	1.74	1000– 1200	1×1×1	2	0	9
<i>Trio, 35248</i>	tfl3d1_16ns\tfl		12-channel	1900	2.92	1100	0.8×0.8×0.8	0	0	2
	tfl3d1_16ns\tfl		12-channel	1900	2.92	1100	1×1×1	0	0	25
	tfl3d1_16ns\tfl		12-channel	2400	3.16	1000	1×1×1	0	0	18

Supplemental Table 2. FDR-corrected p values for group differences

Same as Table 2 but with Benjamini-Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR) correction.

Corrected p values $<.05$ are shown. LHem = left hemisphere. RHem = right hemisphere.

The entry “.0000” means $<.00005$. Most regional least squares means were in the order PTD $<$ TS $<$ TFC. The dagger † indicates a region whose least squares means were in the order PTD $<$ TS $<$ TFC, ‡ indicates TS $>$ PTD $>$ TFC, and * indicates some other order.

Region	Cortical thickness		Surface area	
	p (LHem)	p (RHem)	p (LHem)	p (RHem)
banks of superior temporal sulcus	.0000	.0000		
caudal middle frontal	.0000	.0001		
cuneus	.0000 ‡	.0001 ‡		
fusiform	.0001	.0000		
inferior parietal	.0002	.0114		
inferior temporal	.0003		.0482	
lateral occipital	.0273 *	.0273		
lateral orbitofrontal	.0020	.0101	.0011	.0001
lingual	.0000 ‡	.0012 ‡		
medial orbitofrontal		.0046 *	.0229	.0000
middle temporal	.0000	.0012	.0232	
pars opercularis	.0000	.0006		
pars orbitalis	.0033	.0042		
pars triangularis	.0008			
pericalcarine	.0000 ‡	.0000 ‡		
postcentral		.0273 *		
posterior cingulate			.0307 †	
precentral	.0012	.0482		
precuneus	.0494	.0110		
rostral anterior cingulate	.0176 †	.0042	.0319	.0385 †
rostral middle frontal	.0002 †	.0147 †		
superior frontal	.0001	.0004		
superior temporal	.0000	.0000		
supramarginal	.0029	.0050		
temporal pole	.0114			
transverse temporal		.0114		
insula	.0001	.0063	.0009 †	.0014 †

Supplemental Figure 1. Cortical thickness and surface area versus tic severity in the week preceding the scan.

A: Mean cortical thickness for each child, minus the expected value for that child's age and sex based on the tic-free control group, plotted against the YGTSS total tic score.

B: Same, but for insula surface area.

Supplemental Figure 2. Mean whole-brain cortical thickness decreases with participant age, and does so faster in children with tics.

After adjusting for sex, handedness and scanner, the slope of cortical thickness by age is -0.01 in the TFC group and -0.02 in the combined tic group (PTD and TFC; $p < .001$).

Slope in the PTD and TFC groups do not differ significantly.

Supplemental Figure 3. Increased medial occipital cortex thickness by duration of tic disorder

Mean cortical thickness for each child in a combined medial occipital volume of interest “CLP” (left + right hemisphere cuneus + lingual + pericalcarine cortex) minus the expected value for that child’s age and sex based on the tic-free control group, plotted against duration of tic disorder. The slopes for each group do not differ significantly from zero (PTD group $p = .7$, TS group $p = .076$). Both group means are significantly above zero for the mean of 6 regions. For each of the 6 regions, the corrected p_{FWE} was $< .0003$.

Supplemental Figure 4. Increased medial occipital cortex thickness, by tic severity

Mean cortical thickness for each child in a combined medial occipital volume of interest (left + right hemisphere cuneus + lingual + pericalcarine = “CLP”) minus the expected value for that child’s age and sex based on the tic-free control group, plotted against YGTSS total tic score. The slopes do not differ significantly from zero (PTD $p = .15$, TS $p = .41$).

